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Summary

Arctic PASSION aims to overcome known flaws in the present observing system by refining its operability, improving, and extending pan-Arctic scientific and community-based monitoring and the integration with Indigenous and Local knowledge, by streamlining the access and interoperability of Arctic Data systems and services, and by ensuring the economic viability and sustainability of the observing system for years to come. The ambition of the SAON Roadmap for Arctic Observing and Data Systems (ROADS) is similar: To advance systematic, inclusive, and coordinated Arctic observation to address societal needs, and knowledge gaps across the region. Developed under SAON's 2018–2028 strategic plan, ROADS emphasizes Indigenous participation, shared societal benefits, and integration with existing networks to improve Arctic observing systems.

Key components of the ROADS process are:

- Societal Benefit Assessment: ROADS utilizes frameworks like the *International Arctic Observations Assessment Framework* to align observing systems with societal priorities.
- Shared Arctic Variables (SAVs): SAVs represent measurable phenomena critical to multiple Arctic stakeholders, ensuring coordinated, standardized observations aligned with Indigenous, local, regional and global priorities.
- Governance: The *ROADS Advisory Panel* and *Expert Panels* facilitate definition and implementation, ensuring flexible, phased, and inclusive processes.
- Indigenous Engagement: ROADS seeks to integrate Indigenous Knowledge and leadership through representation and leadership in the *ROADS Advisory Panel* and *Expert Panels*.
- Phased Implementation: ROADS structures observing system improvements through four phases, each guided by structured documentation and *ROADS Advisory Panel* review.

Six Expert Panels are advancing the development of SAVs:

- Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs) (Marine regions of Alaska)
- Permafrost (pan-Arctic focus)
- Salmon and Food Security (Bristol Bay focus)
- Sea Ice and Mobilities (Baffin Bay focus)
- Wildfire – Fennoscandia
- Wildfire – North America

The ROADS process is developing a *documentation framework* for four ROADS phases and for the engagement in the process, and ROADS partners are developing *Societal Benefit Assessment Tools*.

Based on outcomes of recent Arctic Observing Summits¹ and a recently organised survey, these recommendations are formulated:

- Strengthen internal communication between the *Advisory Panel* and *Expert Panels* to clarify roles, goals, and processes.
- Strengthen Indigenous leadership and representation to ensure meaningful participation.
- Improve external communication through making results more visible and accessible.
- Foster relationships with funders and policymakers to secure sustainable implementation.

¹ <https://arcticobservingsummit.org>

- Encourage broader participation and cross-sector collaboration.

Box: Description of deliverable

A status report for the EAVs developed during Arctic PASSION from the perspective of the ROADS process. It will for each EAV provide an overview of their status of development in terms of identification, specification and implementation.

Note: Essential Arctic Variables (EAVs) are referred to as Shared Arctic Variables (SAVs) later in the Arctic PASSION Description of Work.

1. The ROADS process

1.1 Introduction

The Arctic is experiencing environmental and societal changes, which have global implications. Observing and understanding these transformations is vital for informing decision-making, supporting sustainable development, ensuring food security, and mitigating climate impacts. However, the Arctic remains one of the least observed regions on Earth due to coordination challenges, infrastructure gaps, and a lack of systematic planning mechanisms.

In response, *Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks* (SAON) was formed in 2011 to improve the coordination and sustainment of Arctic observations. SAON has proposed the creation of the *Roadmap for Arctic Observing and Data Systems* (ROADS) as part of its 2018–2028 strategy². ROADS seeks to generate a comprehensive, inclusive, and coordinated approach to Arctic observations, addressing critical shortcomings and ensuring that the observing systems prioritize delivering societal benefits.

The Third Arctic Science Ministerial³ (2021) requests as an action for SAON: “Encourage finalizing the Roadmap for Arctic Observing and Data Systems (ROADS) through the coordination and cooperation between national and international programs, small and large projects, and infrastructures, and prioritize implementation”.

1.2 ROADS Vision and Principles

The governance of Arctic observations is polycentric, involving many actors across nations, organizations, disciplines, and Indigenous homelands. Coordination across all is necessary for creating a sustained observing system. ROADS provides a structured, participatory, and adaptable planning framework for Arctic observations and data systems. It is built on these guiding principles (Starkweather *et al.*, 2021):

- Indigenous Peoples’ equitable partnership and funding for their active participation is critical to ROADS;
- All aspects of the ROADS process should support broadly shared benefit from the observing and data systems;
- The ROADS process should complement and integrate, without duplication, the current planning approaches used by existing networks (regional to global), activities, and projects;
- ROADS should support stepwise development through a flexible and evolving structure that allows grassroots identification of themes, infrastructures, and regional foci.

² https://arcticobserving.org/images/pdf/Strategy_and_Implementation/SAON_Strategy_2018-2028_version_16MAY2018.pdf

³ https://asm3.org/library/Files/ASM3_Joint_Statement.pdf

2. The building blocks of ROADS

2.1 Assessment of societal benefits of observing

Current Arctic observations yield valuable information and data that influence community resilience, global models and forecasts, national security decisions, and economic prosperity. However, observations are distributed across a suite of projects, programs and networks and are often constrained by a lack of long-term funding, infrastructure, capacity building, and coordination. In order to make improvements to the Arctic observing system and support broadly shared benefits, it has been proposed that decision-makers require an evidence base that systematically identifies gaps and opportunities for optimized investment. These analyses must recognize the interconnected nature of Arctic observations.

A key innovation of ROADS is its commitment to have focus on societal benefits in observational prioritisation and planning. Traditional Arctic research has often failed to align with the priorities of Indigenous and local communities, focusing instead solely on scientific objectives. The assessment process under ROADS aims to be inclusive and iterative.

The *IDA Science and Technology Policy Institute* (STPI), in collaboration with SAON, led the development of the *International Arctic Observations Assessment Framework* (IAOAF, IDA (2017)). This framework aims to provide a systematic method to evaluate how Arctic observing data contributes to shared and international goals in the Arctic.

STPI and SAON organized a workshop to build international consensus on this framework. The workshop involved experts from government, academia, indigenous organizations, and international research bodies. These experts developed a preliminary version of the framework known as a *value tree*. The foundation of the framework is a *Value Tree Analysis* (VTA), a method used to logically organize how observation inputs (e.g., satellite or sensor data) connect to broader societal benefits. The value tree is hierarchical:

- *Societal Benefit Areas* (SBAs) such as disaster preparedness, marine ecosystems, and infrastructure;
- *Sub-Areas and Key Objectives* (KOs): These define specific needs or actions within each SBA that rely on Earth observation data;
- Links *Key Objectives* to *Key Products, Services, and Outcomes* (KPSOs), and ultimately to the Earth observation inputs needed to produce them.

The final *Arctic Observations Assessment Framework* from the workshop consists of 12 SBAs, 41 SBA Sub-Areas, and 171 Key Objectives. The 12 SBAs are 1) Disaster Preparedness, 2) Environmental Quality, 3) Food Security, 4) Fundamental Understanding of Arctic Systems, 5) Human Health, 6) Infrastructure and Operations, 7) Marine and Coastal Ecosystems and Processes, 8) Natural Resources, 9) Resilient Communities, 10) Sociocultural Services, 11) Terrestrial and Freshwater Ecosystems and Processes, and 12) Weather and Climate.

This full structure allows stakeholders to trace how observations support specific Arctic priorities and help identify which observation systems are most critical. The framework is not developed for the

observing system part; this is left to the application case. Strahlendorff *et al.* (2019) did this for atmosphere and oceanographic observations based on WMO and EU Copernicus program information.

Software tools to support documentation of the application of the IAOAF have been developed by various stakeholders (see sections 5.2 and 5.3). Dobricic *et al.* (2018) used the framework in a comparative study on societal benefit analysis systems of Arctic observing systems.

2.2 Shared Arctic Variables (SAVs)

A coordinated Arctic observing system could enhance data quality, resource efficiency, and cooperation between diverse users, and to achieve this, *Shared Arctic Variables (SAVs)* have been proposed as an organising factor. SAVs are measurable phenomena significant enough to multiple communities and sectors to justify coordinated observation.

Global systems like the *Global Climate Observing System (GCOS)*⁴, *Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS)*⁵, and *Global Cryosphere Watch (GCW)*⁶ use frameworks based on *essential variables* selected by expert panels. These systems standardize data collection and aim for interoperability across nations and agencies. However, they tend to prioritize global needs, often sidelining local or regional priorities. SAVs build on the *essential variable* frameworks used globally but are uniquely adapted to the Arctic by incorporating Indigenous priorities and operational realities like harsh conditions and vast remoteness. The SAV framework combines the best elements of existing models and refines them for Arctic contexts:

- **Shared Importance:** SAVs must be relevant across interests and sectors, including Indigenous communities, scientific agencies, and industries.
- **Measurable Variables:** SAVs focus on phenomena for which clear measurement protocols can be developed.
- **Clustered Observations:** Each SAV is linked to a suite of recommended co-observations to provide necessary environmental context.

The concept of SAVs is further discussed by Bradley *et al.* (2023).

2.3 Governance

Given the complex landscape of Arctic observing initiatives, ROADS has adopted a collaborative governance model with the *ROADS Advisory Panel (AP)* and a series of *Expert Panels (EPs)*. It is a model that leverages existing capacities and provides a scalable mechanism for advancing Arctic observing priorities.

2.3.1 The ROADS Advisory Panel

The ROADS Advisory Panel (AP) was established by the SAON Board in response to a recommendation from the *SAON Roadmap Task Force* to support creating a roadmap to a well-integrated Arctic Observing

⁴ <https://gcos.wmo.int/site/global-climate-observing-system-gcos>

⁵ <https://goosocean.org>

⁶ <https://globalcryospherewatch.org>

System. Appointed by SAON, the AP is meant to guide, coordinate, and integrate the work of thematic and regional EPs. It ensures alignment with ROADS principles, particularly equity and shared benefit.

Terms of Reference⁷ for the AP have been developed which outlines the role of the AP in guiding and advising the implementation of the ROADS process. The principles for the composition of the AP⁸ outline that the AP consists of 15-30 members from observing initiatives, Indigenous representatives, end users of Arctic data and information (e.g. private sector, government, or community decision makers), and funding opportunities or agencies. There are also members from IASC, the SAON Committee on Observations and Networks (CON) and the Arctic Data Committee (ADC).

In parallel with the development of the ROADS process, two major initiatives were developed with the objective also to support to the ROADS process:

- The overall objective of Arctic PASSION⁹, started in 2021, is similar to that of SAON: Arctic PASSION aims to improve current Arctic observing by co-creating an integrated, better coordinated, more useful and more equitable observing system for the Arctic. It does so in international collaboration, including Indigenous Peoples and local communities, that can continuously provide unrestricted, high quality, science-based Earth Observation information tuned to address the urgent needs of people living in the Arctic and have relevance to European and global society.
- *Networking Activities for Sustained Coordinated Observations of Arctic Change (RNA CoObs)*¹⁰: The vision and mission of RNA CoObs are to create meaningful relationships with Indigenous Peoples through the design of Arctic observing and observation systems and to build a community of practice around Arctic observing that serves societal needs and adds shared value for pressing decision-making needs.

These two initiatives have been instrumental in supporting the ROADS process, including establishing and funding several of the EPs as described in chapter 4. The development of the mandates and processes for the AP and the EPs and the development of the understanding of the SAV concept have been under continuous development since the first years of Arctic PASSION and RNA CoObs. Both initiatives have contributed to the development of these overall principles in close interaction with SAON, and there is an overlap in membership across the mentioned initiatives, the SAON Board, and the AP. At the same time, the initiatives have been committed to follow their obligations to their funders; in the case of Arctic PASSION, the European Commission.

2.3.2 Expert Panels

Expert Panels (EPs) are self-organized groups focused on thematic areas that concern one or more SAV. The EPs identify broad themes that will support the development of one or more SAVs. EPs can be initiated by governments, Indigenous organizations, research consortia, or other partners. They develop detailed observation requirements, data strategies, and implementation plans. EPs should consider funding needs, including support for the diverse types of expertise, including Indigenous expertise, that are necessary for ROADS to succeed prior to initiating work. EPs work through a phase approach as

⁷ https://www.arcticobserving.org/images/pdf/ROADS_Advisory_Panel/Mandate_of_the_ROADS_Advisory_Panel.pdf

⁸ https://www.arcticobserving.org/images/pdf/ROADS_Advisory_Panel/Composition_and_Membership_of_the_ROADS_Advisory_Panel.pdf

⁹ <https://arcticpassion.eu>

¹⁰ <https://sites.google.com/alaska.edu/rna-observations>

described in section 2.4. Currently (June 2025), six EPs have been established, and the current status of their work is described in chapter 4.

2.4 A structured, phased and facilitated process

The ROADS process provides a structured, phased approach for improving and integrating Arctic observation systems. It is designed to be collaborative, inclusive, and iterative with guidance and review provided by the ROADS AP at each step.

The four phases of the ROADS process are:

1. **Initiate an Expert Panel:** EPs begin by submitting a brief proposal to the ROADS AP. The proposal includes the scope of assessment, the anticipated benefits, and a list of relevant participants. The AP evaluates alignment with ROADS principles and provides feedback.
2. **Define and assess SAVs:** EP meetings are held with relevant participants to identify and assess SAVs relevant to the EP's scope. The process includes assessments of SAVs' benefit and criticality. Findings are reviewed by the AP before moving to the next step. Coordination is facilitated if multiple EPs are working on overlapping SAVs from different perspectives.
3. **Develop observing and data systems requirements:** In this phase, the EP focuses on defining requirements for each SAV. This includes:
 - Data collection and management (aligned with the FAIR and CARE principles)
 - System design and management
 - Analysis and dissemination needs
 - Connections between requirements and expected outcomes must be outlined.
 - Results are submitted to the AP for review and approval.
4. **Develop implementation strategies:** EPs work with funders and partner organizations to develop strategies for implementation and sustainability. Strategies should address:
 - Technical and organizational infrastructure
 - Financial and human capacity needs
 - Integration of various platforms (satellites, community-led observations, ships, aircraft, autonomous systems)
 - Emphasis is placed on the joint use of infrastructure and the development of value-added services and products.
 - Plans must also include strategies for long-term dissemination and integration.
 - Technological development needs are identified to ensure readiness for future observing systems.

A schematic overview of this *Integrated Advisory Process* and its four phases are found in Figure 1. In order to document the outcomes of each of the four phases, a *documentation framework* has been developed for each phase (see also section 5.1):

- Phase Guidelines
- Phase Documentation Templates
- Phase Evaluation Forms

EPs operate asynchronously, meaning that different panels may be at different phases at any given time. The AP ensures coordination and integration to prevent duplication.

Figure 1: A schematic overview of the *Integrated Advisory Process* and its four phases.

3. Indigenous Engagement in Arctic ROADS

Arctic ROADS aims to improve Arctic observing and data systems through inclusive and equitable collaboration with Indigenous communities whose knowledge and perspectives are relevant to understanding Arctic change. The process aims at ensuring that Indigenous Peoples have not only a voice but also the necessary resources to participate meaningfully.

The history of Indigenous involvement in ROADS builds on earlier recommendations made at events such as the Arctic Observing Summit¹¹ and past Arctic Science Summit Weeks (ASSW)¹². While ROADS is not formally Indigenous-led or co-produced, it does involve Indigenous participation in a consistent manner. The ROADS AP includes six Indigenous experts among its 22 members, representing a move toward meaningful inclusion in governance and strategic planning.

The Indigenous experts of the AP will and have been developing Indigenous Engagement Guidance documents¹³. The document *Indigenous Contexts of SAON's Arctic ROADS* will give an overview of the Indigenous participation in developing Arctic ROADS and Indigenous review processes. The document *Indigenous Protocols, Methodologies, and Practices* will contain key concepts and references to relevant literature and protocols. Finally, the document *Indigenous and Traditional Knowledge Systems* will review key concepts and references relevant to Indigenous Peoples definitions and research ethics. Overall, these documents aim to support Arctic researchers in developing meaningful partnerships with Arctic Indigenous Peoples.

ROADS seeks to continue building a community of practice by advancing documentation and developing tools to support mutual understanding and collaboration. These tools include evaluation metrics that assess success.

¹¹ <https://arcticobservingsummit.org>

¹² <https://www.assw.info>

¹³ <https://roadsadvisorypanel.org/documentation>

4. Overview and status of SAVs

The identification and implementation of Shared Arctic Variables (SAV) are key elements in the ROADS process and in Arctic PASSION, and from its beginning in 2021, Arctic PASSION has been following the principal idea of SAVs. SAVs were inspired by the *essential variable* frameworks and initially described as Essential Arctic Variables (EAV). While EAVs were always envisioned to go beyond the essential variable frameworks in terms of broadly shared use cases understood in an Arctic context, dialog at the 2020 AOS encouraged adopting a more explicit emphasis on ‘shared use’ in the naming.

The RNA CoObs was established in parallel with Arctic PASSION and has the vision and mission to create relationships with Indigenous Peoples. It will design Arctic observing and observation systems and build a community of practice around Arctic observing that serves societal needs and adds shared value for pressing decision-making needs. A Task Team under RNA CoObs is supporting the creation of EPs on SAVs, including identifying potential funding mechanisms to support panels and panel participation.

This chapter provides an overview of the EPs established and currently working and the status of development of the SAVs. Earlier reporting on the SAVs developed under Arctic PASSION is also found in Arctic PASSION deliverable D1.2 (*The definition for the pilot set of Essential Arctic Variables*)¹⁴.

¹⁴ <https://arcticpassion.eu/deliverables/>

4.1 Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs)

The HABs Expert Panel is dedicated to understanding and addressing the increasing impact of harmful algal blooms (HABs) across Alaska’s marine regions. It is led by the Aleut Community of St. Paul Island¹⁵, and the initiative aims to center Indigenous leadership in the development of coordinated monitoring systems, communication strategies, and policy recommendations. The overarching objective is to support coastal communities to maintain resilience and food sovereignty in the face of environmental change.

HABs are a growing concern across Alaska, where warming waters have increased risks from HABs as far north as the Chukchi Sea. These blooms pose serious risks to traditional food sources (also called wild or country foods) such as shellfish (e.g. clams, mussels), seabirds, and marine mammals. The presence of HABs-related neurotoxins in marine subsistence foods has raised serious public health concerns, particularly among Indigenous communities who rely on these for sustenance. Despite this growing threat, there are currently no regulatory standards governing toxin levels in these subsistence foods in Alaska, leaving Indigenous harvesters to rely on their own knowledge and judgment. The EP is working to reduce HABs risks by co-developing guidelines, frameworks, and outreach materials that support informed, community-driven decision-making.

The EP defines these concepts to guide its work: Food sovereignty is understood as the right of Indigenous Peoples to define their own sustainable food systems; Resilience refers to the ability of marine food systems to withstand and adapt to disruptions; Adaptation involves the emergence of new practices that maintain essential subsistence activities despite environmental change; Health is viewed holistically and emphasizes both access to safe, nutritious food and the ability to sustain cultural traditions; Safety is focused on minimizing the risks associated with harvesting and consuming potentially contaminated foods.

To assess and communicate its relevance, the EP draws on the International Arctic Observations Assessment Framework (IAOAF, IDA (2017)), as well as a Theory of Change framework, focusing on societal benefits related to food security, human health, natural resources, community resilience, and sociocultural services.

Funding for the EP comes from a combination of public and private sources, including the Northern Latitudes Partnership¹⁶, Alaska Ocean Observing System¹⁷ and the NOAA NCCOS SEAHABs program¹⁸. Additional support is being pursued to ensure adequate compensation for EP members’ participation and sustain community workshops.

Communication among EP members is maintained through regular meetings and will be augmented by digital platforms such as the Indigenous Sentinels Network (ISN) for data sharing and knowledge production¹⁹. The project also plans to host an in-person workshop on St. Paul Island in early 2026 to foster relationship-building and strategic planning. Communication practices are rooted in co-

¹⁵ <https://www.aleut.com>

¹⁶ <https://www.northernlatitudes.org>

¹⁷ <https://aoots.org>

¹⁸ <https://coastalscience.noaa.gov/science-areas/habs/seahab>

¹⁹ <https://www.sentinelsnetwork.com>

production principles, ensuring that internal coordination is inclusive and adaptive, while external messaging reflects the collective input and consent of all participants. Recruitment is underway for a new early-career Indigenous co-lead to continue integrating Indigenous perspectives at all stages of the initiative.

Overall status: The EP has submitted the Phase I documentation package²⁰.

²⁰ <https://roadsadvisorypanel.org/expert-panel?view=article&id=20:salmon-and-food-security-expert-panel-2&catid=2:uncategorised>

4.2 Permafrost

The EP focuses on the challenges related to permafrost in the Arctic. The aim is to enhance the sharing of information, observations, and management practices to support better-informed decision-making across Arctic communities. Given that many Arctic settlements are located on permafrost, understanding and managing the impacts of its thawing is vital for sustaining infrastructure, preserving ecosystems, respecting cultural practices, ensuring health and safety, and contributing to global climate understanding.

The established panel has taken a pan-Arctic approach, initially concentrating on the western Arctic while seeking to incorporate insights from the Russian Arctic when possible. It brings together a diverse group of experts, including those with indigenous and local knowledge, as well as scientists from social, medical, engineering, and natural science backgrounds. By integrating these varied perspectives, the panel aims to foster a transdisciplinary understanding of permafrost and develop more inclusive and equitable ways of sharing information.

The panel will build on the existing efforts, bringing together expertise, lessons learnt and the ongoing efforts from three European Union's Horizon 2020 projects *Nunataryuk*²¹, Arctic PASSION and *GreenFeedBack*²², the *Catchment2Coast* Fram Centre project²³, and the indigenous expertise from the Hamlet of Tuktoyaktuk in Northwest Territories in Canada, as well as local knowledge from Longyearbyen in Svalbard.

One of the primary goals is to overcome the systemic shortcomings in Arctic observing and data systems. These include fragmented communication across communities and scientific disciplines, insufficient integration of local and indigenous observations, and a lack of accessible and respectful data-sharing mechanisms.

The societal relevance of this work is significant. Permafrost degradation affects infrastructure, ecosystem stability, resource management, and cultural practices. It also plays a critical role in climate feedback due to the release of greenhouse gases. Through the use of the International Arctic Observing Assessment Framework (IDA, 2017) and other evaluation tools, the EP has assessed the societal benefits of its work and aims to deliver outcomes that support both local adaptation strategies and broader scientific goals.

Potential SAVs that are under discussion include measurements of permafrost temperature, active layer thickness, ground ice content, and self-perceived human health-related indicators.

Overall status: The EP has submitted the Phase I²⁴ and Phase II²⁵ documentation packages.

²¹ <https://www.nunataryuk.org>

²² <https://eu-greenfeedback.com>

²³ <https://www.niva.no/en/projects/c2c>

²⁴ https://roadsadvisorypanel.org/images/Expert_Panels/Permafrost/ROADS%20Permafrost%20Phase%20I%20-%20EP%20proposal%20-%20Submitted%2015JAN2024.pdf

²⁵

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1EFCsRAqddlhRSX9nqs7LxtwMw3vFONzm/edit?usp=drive_link&ouid=100978649835470979475&rtpof=true&sd=true

4.3 Salmon and Food Security

The Expert Panel focuses on improving salmon observation in the Bristol Bay watershed of Alaska with a focus on Chinook or king salmon. The project emphasizes the integration of Indigenous knowledge, scientific research, and community priorities to support the well-being of local populations, particularly Indigenous communities.

The panel seeks to address critical gaps in current salmon monitoring by developing equitable, community-driven approaches. Bristol Bay was selected for its ecological significance when it comes to salmon and existing relationships with the primary facilitators. The region's healthy ecosystem and active subsistence and commercial fisheries provide a unique opportunity to design a robust observation system that could serve as a model for other Arctic areas.

The EP will work with the Arctic Data Center to develop a Salmon Data Portal to show observational assets and changes in funding over time. Additional goals include fostering local workforce development, ensuring the inclusion of social and cultural knowledge in research, and applying the "Two-Eyed Seeing" framework, which blends Indigenous and Western ways of knowing. These efforts are designed to enhance sustainability, foster cross-sector collaboration, and enable local communities to have a stronger voice in research and policy decisions.

From the International Arctic Observing Assessment Framework (IAOAF, IDA (2017)) ten benefit areas have been identified as relevant to the work of this EP. They are: 1) Disaster Preparedness, 2) Environmental, Quality, 3) Food Security, 4) Human Health, 5) Infrastructure and Operations, 6) Marine and Coastal Ecosystems and Processes, 7) Natural Resources, 8) Resilient Communities, 9) Sociocultural Services, and 10) Terrestrial and Freshwater Ecosystems and Processes.

The EP is convened by the RNA CoObs and brings together a diverse group of contributors, including Indigenous leaders, fisheries scientists, policy experts, and academic researchers. The initiative is supported by funding from the Sasakawa Peace Foundation and NOAA.

Overall status: The EP has submitted the Phase I documentation package²⁶.

²⁶ https://drive.google.com/file/d/1hetsTWdAlAXgRZDy2fJgPUmSX7twCEQ9/view?usp=drive_link

4.4 Sea ice

Sea ice is a defining feature of the North and for many is synonymous with the Arctic. It is a platform for life, and for centuries a reliable platform for travel. However, in recent decades sea ice variability and absence has characterized the region and the cascading effects of these changes have influenced all aspects of life. Human-induced climate change has led to the decline in multi-year ice and year-to-year changes in seasonal sea ice cover. These changes bring with them risks, challenges and opportunities affecting all Arctic communities, pan-Arctic sectors, and global actors alike; therefore, continued, coordinated observation is crucial. In addition to environmental importance, sea ice also holds significant economic and cultural significance. As such, the focus of this EP is on sea ice and mobilities²⁷

The geographic scope of the EP is the Baffin Bay region, from Ellesmere Island, south to Nunatsiavut. The region enjoys significant political, scientific, economic, and institutional cooperation, which includes both Canadian and Greenlandic communities with cultural and subsistence ties. Indigenous Peoples, regulatory bodies, and co-management entities on both sides of Baffin Bay, are presented with a growing number of challenges related to changes in sea ice, and the resulting increased accessibility to the region. Most notably these challenges include changes to mobility and community-based needs, loss of ice impacts on wildlife and ecosystem(s) including, increased shipping, and economic development: lack of suitable infrastructure to support population growth, increased societal tensions, opportunities for wage labor, risk of pollution.

The purpose of this EP is to improve the coordination and relevance of sea ice observation in the Baffin Bay region. There is shared concern that current Arctic Observing System inputs are performing poorly and with little or no input regarding priorities from local communities or Indigenous Peoples. The EP aims to prioritize societal benefit in the variable identification and selection process.

The EP is made up of sea ice specialists from Canada and Greenland, comprising individuals from Indigenous communities and organizations, academia, industry, government, and regulatory bodies. At present, Phase I documentation has been submitted and reviewed by the AP. An in-person meeting of the EP was held in Ottawa, Canada in January of 2025. The panel is in the process of developing and employing its own Societal Benefit Assessment Framework as it works through Phase II of the ROADS process. A second in-person meeting will be held in Nuuk, Greenland in November 2025, coinciding with Greenland Science Week.

The Sea Ice Expert Panel is a joint European-Canadian effort under the umbrella of Arctic PASSION which is funded by the EU Horizon 2020 programme and New Frontiers in Research Fund Canada. Phase I and early Phase II activities were funded through the UK Arctic Office. Funding for Phases II through IV was secured through Nordforsk in the Spring of 2025.

Overall status: The EP has submitted the Phase I documentation package²⁸.

²⁷ Mobilities is defined as the movement of people and goods on frozen sea ice or within ice covered waters (e.g., sledge, snowmobile, or personal watercraft, commercial vessel, etc.) and includes both local mobilities (e.g. Individual community members' movement on frozen sea-ice and within ice infested waters) and regional and global traffic moving through the Arctic) for purposes of fisheries, tourism, resource extraction, and re-supply, to name a few.

²⁸ https://docs.google.com/document/d/1vymHJLaSeTAIAct8D17Hf9cUNyFicull4K3N1Vltlq0/edit?usp=drive_link

4.5 Wildfire Expert Panel - Fennoscandia

The EP was initiated as the first through an expert workshop in Finland in 2022, supported through a national wildfire project to enable equitable support to the participating Indigenous and local experts. This kind of support was difficult in the Arctic PASSION project, so it was fortunate to be able to extend this effort with extra national funding. The work focuses on creating the ignition identification SAV accompanied by predictive services to forecast wildfire impacts using weather data.

The initial experts workshop identified three primary SAVs topics: ignition sites and protection needs, soil and vegetation moisture, and prescribed burning. Each variable candidate was selected based on societal and environmental relevance, with special attention to Indigenous Sámi knowledge and practices. Ignition sites are closely linked to human activities such as tourism locations, off-road vehicle routes, infrastructure heating, as well as natural causes like lightning - special locations information. Loss of grazing land from fires has devastating impacts on reindeer herding, a critical livelihood for Sámi communities. Soil and vegetation moisture is equally vital; drying landscapes and increased shrubification, exacerbated by global warming, have heightened wildfire risks - a continuous map updating exercise. Prescribed burning was a particular example of the need to monitor human activities as one aspect of a wildfire SAV.

The next workshops with over a dozen more subject matter experts examined the societal importance of these SAVs in relation to wildfire prevention, community resilience, and the protection of natural resources like reindeer pastures and forests. Wildfires contribute to greenhouse gas emissions and climate change, further threatening Arctic environments. Identifying ignition points and predicting wildfire risks helps local communities to extinguish fires and minimize damage early. Enhanced use of satellite monitoring, drone surveillance, and microclimate models are proposed to improve detection and response capabilities.

The work also connected wildfire preparedness to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), emphasizing the need for climate adaptation, disaster risk reduction, and the protection of land ecosystems. The expanded EP documented the societal relevance of a wildfire SAV using the International Arctic Observing Assessment Framework (IAOAF, IDA (2017)) *Value Tree Analysis*. The experts identified 49 links between wildfire SAVs and *Key Objectives* across six societal benefit areas: Infrastructure and Operations, Natural Resources, Disaster Resilience, Resilient Communities, Weather and Climate, and Human Health. The main finding from the societal benefit assessment was that wildfire SAVs are critical across a wide range of Arctic societal concerns. Infrastructure must be protected through timely risk warnings. Natural resource exploitation activities need to incorporate fire risk information to ensure safe operations. Emergency preparedness must improve to address human-made fire hazards, particularly with the growing risk posed by inexperienced tourists. Building resilient communities relies on blending traditional knowledge and new technologies, such as drones. Disseminating accessible weather and wildfire risk information helps to protect lives and property, while recognizing the profound mental health impacts wildfires have on livelihoods like reindeer herding.

The candidate SAVs merged for further development as *Ignition Identification*, acknowledging existing GCOS ECVs and other actions that need no replication. Identifying real wildfires with an updated understanding of the state of the surrounding terrain is a missing part aiming to quickly detect and

attribute fire ignitions, understand the causes, enable faster analysis and actions to prevent spread. Recognizing ignition points, especially in areas with tourism and other human activity, was seen as essential. Dry forest heaths, lightning-prone ridges, and peatlands are identified as particularly vulnerable landscapes. Ignition detection efforts would leverage satellite imagery, lightning data, fire weather forecasts, community observations, and traditional Indigenous knowledge.

Figure 2: Overall process description behind the SAV *Ignition Identification*

The report explains that although much global and national data infrastructure for wildfire monitoring exists, there are still gaps, especially regarding terrain moisture state, which community-based data collection and integration of Indigenous knowledge could improve. Current systems like satellite monitoring and weather modeling can be detailed a lot with local observations and better regional coordination of collecting terrain moisture state information.

The Expert Panel's fourth workshop in Inari, Finland, in 2023, concentrated on developing requirements and planning how to combine the many information flows into a system. Information was gathered related to different elements of the *Ignition Identification SAV*: human activities, ignition detection and fire prone terrain. Diagrams were made (Figure 2) showing key data flows and the entities having/producing these to be included for this Wildfire SAV. Phase III documentation will be finished when guidelines for the documentation have been developed (see section 5.1).

At the moment, there is a mobile application under development to enable people going to nature to give their observations about terrain moisture. It should help to refine satellite soil moisture data and

help to identify areas that are prone to wildfires. Opportunities arising from this work include developing a service that integrates fire risk assessments with real-time detection of fire events, attributing causes based on human activity and terrain sensitivity. Advances in satellite observation, combined with local field observations, would allow for more precise identification of fire-prone areas and improve rapid response capabilities.

This work has a new Finnish funding source until April 2026. In addition to developing the local observing app, there is also other work to prepare for Phase IV with a networking exercise to gather Nordic country partners for a Northern European demonstration of the Wildfire SAV.

Overall status: The EP has submitted the Phase I and II documentation packages²⁹. Phase III documentation is about to be submitted.

²⁹ <https://roadsadvisorypanel.org/expert-panel?view=article&id=15:wildfire-expert-panel&catid=2:uncategorised>

4.6 Wildfire Expert Panel - North America

The International Arctic Research Center at University of Alaska Fairbanks (UAF) will initiate an EP on the theme of wildfire, regionally focused on Alaska and the wider North American Arctic. There are already many existing data systems to support this theme, but these are largely focused on the fire management community and have limited involvement with Indigenous communities. Improving alignment and convergence of the community and management perspectives and expectations is therefore a cornerstone of this effort on the path to achieving the ROADS process objective to design equitable and well-defined observing and data systems that support societal benefits. Communication is relatively easy between national scientists and agencies, but a perspective change is needed to strengthen community and global engagement and foreground Indigenous perspectives. The EP looks to address this by focusing initial efforts on networking, rather than purely on observations. The context specific to Alaska and boreal Canada includes prescribed or cultural burning, subsistence use of the land and development of agriculture, and the widespread impact of smoke. While the people inhabiting the boreal forest regions have long-standing adaptations to living in a fire-prone ecosystem, increases in wildfire incidence in, for example, south-western Alaska are recent and of great concern to communities. Overall, wildfire incidence as measured by factors such as burned area, has increased. The 2023 season in Canada, for example, broke all records, temporarily displacing more than half of the population of the North-West Territories

Workshops were held at the University of Alaska Fairbanks (International Arctic Research Center) in August 2024 as a breakout session during the RNA CoObs all-hands meeting, and at the Alaska Forum on the Environment (AFE) in February 2025. Both were scheduled within larger events to be able to attract potential EP members. Between the two workshops, approx. 40 participants from various sectors across Alaska and Canada (Indigenous/tribal/First Nation government, land management agencies, municipal and state government, and universities) were reached. The RNA CoObs breakout session included a faculty member from the UAF College of Indigenous Studies, fire managers (fire meteorologists, fire ecologists), and providers of remote sensing data. The Alaska Fire Science Consortium, as a boundary organization connecting researchers with the wildland fire management community, was also identified as a valuable partner. Key insights from this session revolved around strategies of communicating to and recruiting Indigenous and community EP members. Offering a convincing value proposition to Indigenous experts (“Why should you participate / what benefit do you receive from participating”) prompted us to frame EP involvement from the outset around the notion of societal and community benefits. The AFE workshop was therefore designed to include group work to elicit themes that potentially connect to data system needs and societal benefits, in an open-ended fashion. Initial themes that emerged were the ability to manage environmental health (pollution, smoke, mental health) and natural resources (ecosystems and food security, including impacts on permafrost, timber access), local disaster preparedness (brush clearing, prescribed burning, hazard mapping and mitigation), and incident management (fire danger). There is also interest in integrating EP efforts to existing training and educational structures. Connections were made with the Bristol Bay Native Association, Tanana Chiefs Conference, the Knik Tribe, and the Samba Ké First Nation in Canada. A sample of the AFE group work template was completed by one break-out group, and a panorama of the diverse themes that emerged, are provided in Figure 3. A status report of the North American Wildfire EP was also presented at the Arctic Science Summit Week in Boulder, Colorado, USA in March 2025.

4.7 Expert Panels and the development of SAVs. General status

The process to establish EPs and for these to develop SAVs has been ongoing since the initiation of Arctic PASSION and RNA CoObs. Key aspects of the process to be further developed include³⁰:

- Formulating a ‘value proposition’. Participants in the EPs will ask ‘what is in it for me’?
- Engaging Indigenous organizations and their representatives has been more difficult than anticipated, mainly due to the capacity of these combined with a lack of funding from projects supporting EPs to directly fund Indigenous expert engagement.
- Throughout the process, there has been a discussion of the balance between Indigenous, local, regional, and global interests. The expectations to the Expert Plan include that there should be significant Indigenous representation, and preferably in a leadership role. This has led non-Arctic nations to ask how they could be engaged and how the process could also support their national interests.
- Through the documentation process, there has been a tendency to seek to standardise the work across EPs, which has not always been possible.
- Longer-term funding of the EPs.

Less tangible conclusions from the process include:

- Engaging in the process requires need for patience and flexibility.
- The rapid changes in the Arctic emphasize the urgency of the issues to organize Arctic observing. In the light of this, it can be difficult to see the value of a process that works on a yearly scale.
- The process itself has already been beneficial in making connections and networks, independent of the outcome.

See also Chapter 6: *Recommendations for the development of the Arctic ROADS process.*

³⁰ These conclusions also come from a survey organised by Alice Bradly: *SAON ROADS / Lessons Learned / Anonymized summaries of input*: <https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1-lEoxo990kYIPYOnUogtPFVq1IWmfnfSuvDvP5HrDEDY/edit#slide=id.p>

5. Overview and status of Arctic ROADS Tools

5.1 Documentation framework

The AP is developing and maintaining a framework for the documentation of the ROADS process³¹. It includes these components:

- *Understanding the SAON ROADS process*: Includes broad overviews of SAON ROADS for a range of audiences, including basic definitions and key diagrams.
- *Participating in the SAON ROADS process through an Expert Panel*: Includes all the resources and documentation that those initiating an EP will need to successfully initiate and complete the ROADS process.
- *Serving on the SAON ROADS Advisory Panel*: Includes all of the basic recruitment, on-boarding, workplan, self-reflection and terms of reference required for AP members to fully understand their roles and responsibilities in the SAON ROADS process.
- *Documenting the SAON ROADS process*: Includes all of the basic documentation tools of the *Integrated Advisory Process*.
- *Promoting and developing the SAON ROADS process*: Includes guidance related to engagement and continuing to develop the tools of the SAON ROADS process.

Guidelines for the four ROADS phases are found in the section *Participating in the SAON ROADS process through an Expert Panel*, while the actual templates for documenting the phases are found in the section *Documenting the SAON ROADS process*. As of June 2025, the development of the documentation framework for the documentation and evaluation of the four phases is complete for Phase I and II, while it is under development for Phase III.

5.2 Societal benefit framework / Evaluation tools

As described in section 2.1, a societal benefit assessment illustrates links between observing systems, data products, and applications and shows how they connect to societal benefit. The assessment process includes giving capabilities and gaps numerical ratings and written descriptions. Ratings are given for a particular context by an individual or small team of experts. The resulting diagram creates a visual representation of the observing system.

The US Arctic Observing Network (US AON) has developed a Benefit Tool³² with underlying methods. The tool has been used to evaluate a subset of the Arctic PASSION Pilot Services, and the preliminary results are described in section 5.3.

Similarly, the Finland Meteorological Institute (FMI) has developed a value tree tool and has published the results of applying the tool (FMI, 2019). Physical atmosphere measurements and ocean variables were linked to key products, outcomes or services and to key objectives of the assessment framework. In a workshop, the costs of earth observing inputs and modelling components were estimated by experts or estimated based on European Union projects or Copernicus program tenders. The WMO OSCAR database for satellite and surface observation systems north of 60°N was used for numbers of the different station and mission categories in the Arctic. It was concluded that the total yearly value of

³¹ <https://roadsadvisorypanel.org/documentation>

³² <https://usaon.org/evaluation-and-planning/benefit-tool> and www.usaon.org/apps/benefit-tool

this observation system is over 204 million €. Compared to the observing system estimated costs in the area 30°N to 60°N this is only about a fifth, and it was concluded that the Arctic is under-observed.

5.3 Evaluating Arctic PASSION Pilot Services

There is a close connection between the SAVs and the Arctic PASSION Pilot Services. The aim of Arctic PASSION Work Package 5 is to demonstrate the societal and economic value of the Pilot Services, and the outcome of the WP analysis is found in deliverable D5.3 (*Arctic services impact assessments and generalization*)³³.

The US Arctic Observing Network (US AON) Benefit Tool³⁴ has evaluated a subset of Arctic PASSION Pilot Services. As described above, the tool illustrates links between observing systems, data products, and applications and shows how they connect to societal benefit.

In the evaluation, Pilot Service leads have gone through these steps:

- 1) Defined the societal impacts that are the intended outcomes of the Pilot Service.
- 2) Aligned these outcomes with the International Arctic Observing Assessment Framework (IAOAF, IDA (2017))
- 3) Defined Objects: Identified intermediate products and observing systems that support the Pilot Service.
- 4) Defined Links: Established connections between defined objects and assessed their contribution to the performance of the Pilot Service.

The tool generates a *Sankey diagram*, which depicts relationships (shown as links defined in step 4) between distinct efforts (as defined in step 3). The ambition is to evaluate all Arctic PASSION Pilot Services, and as of June 2025 Pilot Services 1, 4, 5, 6, and 8 have been evaluated. The Sankey diagrams for these are found in Figure 4. A more formal and complete reporting of this evaluation is expected later in 2025.

³³ <https://arcticpassion.eu/deliverables/>

³⁴ <https://usaon.org/evaluation-and-planning/benefit-tool> and www.usaon.org/apps/benefit-tool

Figure 4: Sankey diagrams for the US AON Benefit Tool evaluation of Arctic PASSION Pilot Services 1, 4, 5, 6, and 8.

The process is described in more detail in Shapiro, Starkweather *et al.* (2025).

6. Recommendations for the development of the Arctic ROADS process

Establishing the Arctic ROADS process has been the theme of the Arctic Observing Summits since 2020³⁵. The AP held its first meeting in December 2021, thereby formally initiating the ROADS process. In spring 2025, the AP initiated a survey, raising these two questions: 1) *Are we doing the right thing?* and 2) *Who is this process meaningful for?* The outcome of the survey as of May 2025 is found in Annex 2.

Based on the AOS discussions and on the survey, the AP has formulated a series of recommendations for the further development of the Arctic ROADS process.

Unless noted, the actions below are for the AP:

- **Improve ‘internal’ communication between the EPs and AP to clarify roles, goals, and processes:**
 - Establish a Community of Practice (CoP) for facilitators working on all EPs of the ROADS Process.
 - Strengthen the current “Open Partnership Meeting” practice of the AP.
 - Strengthen alignment with data specialists to support Expert Panels.
 - Develop a unified set of documentation on the ROADS process and include accessible graphics and plain language summaries about high level goals.
 - Have a purpose statement and simplify language to be direct and to the point. Make sure that the goals of each phase are clearly understandable without deep knowledge of the process.
 - Have roles clearly identified and work through positionality of the AP, including roles external to the AP.
 - Document methodologies used for Societal Benefit Analysis.
- **Strengthen Indigenous leadership and representation on AP and EPs:**
 - Have a process for ad hoc review of the documentation and evaluation processes by Indigenous groups, especially the Permanent Participants.
 - Facilitate ad hoc review of EPs by relevant expertise for the Indigenous groups involved in the EP, e.g. Saami Council review for EPs with Saami involvement, ICC for those with Inuit partnership, etc.
 - Ensure the process reflects societal needs, particularly by involving Indigenous groups and Arctic municipalities [AOS 2024 recommendation].
- **Improve ‘external’ communication through making results more visible and accessible:**
 - Improve science communication and build this into funding requests.
 - Work with APECS to initiate a “ROADS explainer reel” competition, juried by the SAON Board. Identify budget for small prizes and showcase top 3 videos.
 - Revisit the draft *Engagement Strategy*. This is also tied to the above ‘Strengthen Indigenous leadership and representation on AP and EPs’.
 - Consider the four phases of the ROADS Process as each producing something of inherent value. Be clear in the process description that both the process itself (for the people and groups involved) and the intermediate products are value-adds from the process. Materials

³⁵ https://docs.google.com/document/d/1XBWpjpZqIGmlr7hf_bjn8Ev-tgC9IliMrZQS4_76tcg/edit?usp=sharing

- should be created in each phase to communicate processes, results and benefits to broad external audiences.
- Highlight patterns across the EPs as they are broad concepts to push the field forward [AOS recommendation] [Action item for AP and EPs].
- **Foster stronger ties with funders and policy-makers throughout the process so that Phase IV implementation is viable and sustainable:**
 - Improve coordination across fragmented authorities, including involving decision-makers from Arctic states [AOS 2024 Recommendation].
 - Create a draft description of policymaker and funder roles within EPs for the EPs to adapt to their context.
 - Identify a new Arctic Science Funders Forum representative for the AP.
 - Host mini-workshop series on policy and funding successes, e.g. Indigenous Guardians Network in Canada, ArcticNET, etc.
 - **Encourage broader participation and cross-sector collaboration:**
 - Involvement of early career focused groups across sectors. Consider an *Early Career Researcher* (ECR) seat on the AP.
 - Consider what strategic growth looks like in this context: What broader participation do we have the capacity to support, and target outreach accordingly [Action item for the SAON Board].
 - Consider the AP to have a member of the committee for the International Polar Year (IPY).
 - Through earlier AOSs and in the earlier stages of the ROADS process, there were dialogues with experts that worked with questions at a pan-Arctic scale, or global scale. Strengthen collaboration with these.
 - Host conference workshops, dialogues, and panels on specific topics relevant to ROADS (Indigenous engagement, benefit assessments, data, etc.), but do not go into detail about ROADS since this can be overwhelming - suggestion to just mention it at the end [Action item for AP and EPs].
 - Create a recommended funding scheme for participation.
 - Consider the process of establishing an EP from the perspective of a non-Arctic State. What are the challenges, and how can the AP be a facilitator?

References

Cited in this document:

Arctic PASSION: The definition for the pilot set of Essential Arctic Variables (Deliverable D1.2).
<https://nextcloud.awi.de/s/Tni792iZnaSL0C4>.

Arctic PASSION: Arctic services impact assessments and generalization (Deliverable 5.3).
<https://arcticpassion.eu/deliverables>.

Bradley, A., Eicken, H., Lee, O., Gebruk, A., & Pirazzinie, R. (2023): Shared Arctic Variable Framework Links Local to Global Observing System Priorities and Requirements. *Arctic*, 74(5).
<https://doi.org/10.14430/arctic76429>.

Dobricic S., Monforti Ferrario F., Pozzoli L., Wilson J., Gambardella A., Tilche A., Impact assessment study on societal benefits of Arctic observing systems - IMOBAR, EUR 29400 EN, Publication Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2018, ISBN 978-92- 79-96697-2, <https://doi.org/10.2760/713084>, JRC113327.

IDA Science and Technology Policy Institute and Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks. 2017. International Arctic Observations Assessment Framework. IDA Science and Technology Policy Institute, Washington, DC, U.S.A., and Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks, Oslo, Norway, 73 pp.
<https://arcticobserving.org/images/pdf/misc/STPI-SAON-International-Arctic-Observations-Framework-Report-2017.pdf>.

Shapiro H., Starkweather S. *et al*: Benefit Assessment - A Collaborative Methodology to Understand Gaps and Strengths in the Arctic Observing System, 2025. In prep for *Weather, Climate and Society*.

Starkweather S., Jan R. Larsen, Eva Krueemmel, Hajo Eicken, David Arthurs, Alice C. Bradley, Nikoosh Carlo, Tom Christensen, Raychelle Daniel, Finn Danielsen, Sarah Kalhok, Michael Karcher, Margareta Johansson, Halldór Jóhannsson, Yuji Kodama, Sten Lund, Maribeth S. Murray, Tuukka Petäjä, Peter L. Pulsifer, Stein Sandven, Ravi D. Sankar, Mikko Strahlendorff, Jeremy Wilkinson (2021): Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks' (SAON) Roadmap for Arctic Observing and Data Systems (ROADS).
<https://journalhosting.ucalgary.ca/index.php/arctic/article/view/74330>
<https://doi.org/10.14430/arctic74330>.

Strahlendorff, Mikko; Veijola, Katriina; Gallo, Jason; Vitale, Vito; Hannele, Savela; Smirnov, Alexander; Tanaka, Hajime; Sueyoshi, Tetsuo; Nitu, Rodica; Larsen, Jan René: Value tree for physical atmosphere and ocean observations in the Arctic (2019). FMI publications. <https://helda.helsinki.fi/items/81020beb-c6d0-4f44-a75d-e0d503edde01>.

Other relevant documentation:

Chythlook, C., Rudolf, M., Biermann, M., Eicken, H., & Starkweather, S. (2022) Research networking activities support sustained coordinated observations of Arctic change. *Oceanography*, 35.
<https://doi.org/10.5670/oceanog.2022.110>.

Eicken, H., Danielsen, F., Sam J-M, Fidel, M., Johnson, N., et al. (2021) Connecting Top-Down and Bottom-Up Approaches in Environmental Observing. *BioScience*, 71.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/biab018>.

Feddern, M.L., Schoen, E.R., Shaftel, R., Cunningham, C.J., Chythlook, C., Connors, B.M., Murdoch, A.D., von Biela, V.R. and Woods, B., 2023. Kings of the North: Bridging Disciplines to Understand the Effects of Changing Climate on Chinook Salmon in the Arctic–Yukon–Kuskokwim Region. *Fisheries*, 48(8).
<https://doi.org/10.1002/fsh.10923>.

Loose, N. & Heimbach, P. (2021) Leveraging uncertainty quantification to design ocean climate observing systems. *Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020MS002386>.

Nguyen, A., Pillar, H., Ocaña, V., Bigdeli, A., Smith, T., & Heimbach, P. (2021) The Arctic Subpolar gyre sTate Estimate: Description and assessment of a data-constrained, dynamically consistent ocean-sea ice estimate for 2002–2017. *Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems*, 13.
<https://doi.org/10.1029/2020MS002398>.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

		URL
ACA	Arctic Circle Assembly	https://www.arcticcircle.org/assemblies
ADC	IASC and SAON Arctic Data Committee	https://arcticdc.org
AOS	Arctic Observing Summit	https://arcticobservingsummit.org
AP	ROADS Advisory Panel	https://roadsadvisorypanel.org
APECS	Association of Polar Early Career Scientists	https://www.apecs.is
CARE	The CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance are a set of principles intended to guide open data projects in engaging Indigenous Peoples rights and interests. CARE is an acronym which stands for Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics	
CON	SAON Committee on Observations and Networks	https://www.arcticobserving.org/committees/con/meetings
ECR	Early Career Researcher	
ECV	Essential Climate Variable	
EO	Earth Observations	
EP	Expert Panel	
FAIR	FAIR data is data which meets the FAIR principles of findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability	
GCW	Global Cryosphere Watch	https://globalcryospherewatch.org/
GCOS	Global Climate Observing System	https://gcos.wmo.int/site/global-climate-observing-system-gcos
GOOS	Global Ocean Observing System	https://goosocean.org/

IAP	Integrated Advisory Process (of ROADS)	
IASC	International Arctic Science Committee	https://iasc.info
ICC	Indigenous Circumpolar Council	https://www.inuitcircumpolar.com
IPY	International Polar Year	
KO	Key Objective (as defined in IDA, 2017)	
NOAA	US National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration	https://www.noaa.gov
RNA CoOBS	Research Networking Activities for Sustained Coordinated Observations of Arctic Change (RNA CoObs)	https://sites.google.com/alaska.edu/rna-observations
(Arctic) ROADS	SAON Roadmap for Arctic Observing and Data Systems (ROADS)	
SAON	Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks	https://arcticobserving.org
SAV	Shared Arctic Variable	
SBA	Societal Benefit Area	
US AON	US Arctic Observing Network	https://usaon.org
WMO	World Meteorological Organisation	https://wmo.int
WMO OSCAR	WMO Observing Systems Capability Analysis and Review Tool	https://space.oscar.wmo.int/

Annex 1. Event overview

The ROADS process and the work of the Expert Panels have been the topic at several events, including the list below.

Physical Advisory Panel meetings, which were also *Open Partnership meetings*³⁶:

- Arctic Circle Assembly, Reykjavik, Iceland, October 2022
- Arctic Circle Assembly, Reykjavik, Iceland, October 2023
- ASSW 2024, Edinburgh, March 2024

Activities during Arctic Observing Summit³⁷ include:

- 2020: Five Working Group sessions: 1) Design, Optimization and Implementation of the Observing System, 2) Observing in Support of Adaptation and Mitigation, 3) Observing in Support of Indigenous Food Security and Related Needs, 4) Data Interoperability and Federated Search, 5) Arctic Observations in the context of Global Observing initiatives (March, online, Akureyri, Iceland)
- 2022: Six Working Group sessions: 1) Food security, 2) Regional to Global Observing, 3) Data Sharing, 4) System Integration, 5) Utility and Benefits, and 6) Capacity Sharing (March, Tromsø, Norway)
- 2024: Four Working Group sessions: 1) Regional to Global Observing, 2) Data Sharing, 3) System Implementation/SAON ROADS, 4) Observing System Benefits (March, Edinburgh, Scotland)

Activities during Arctic Circle Assembly (Reykjavik, Iceland)³⁸ include:

- 2021: Advancing SAON's Roadmap through regional and global capabilities (session)
- 2022:
 - Roadmap for Arctic Observing and Data Systems (ROADS) - Shared Arctic Variables (session)
 - Wildfires: A Shared Arctic Variable (session)
 - Permafrost as a Shared Arctic Variable (EP workshop)
- 2023:
 - Strategies for Arctic observations: Empowering Indigenous and local perspectives
 - Permafrost as a Shared Arctic Variable (EP workshop)
- 2024: Permafrost as a Shared Arctic Variable (EP workshop)

Activities during Arctic Frontiers (Tromsø, Norway)³⁹, include:

- 2022: A Roadmap for Arctic Observing and Data Systems (ROADS) (presentation)
- 2023: A Roadmap for Arctic Observing and Data Systems (ROADS) (presentation)
- 2024:
 - Observing the Arctic: Empowering indigenous and local perspectives (poster)
 - Shared Arctic Variable definition on theme permafrost (poster)

Sessions at Arctic Science Summit Week (ASSW)

- 2021: Advancing SAON's Roadmap etc. through Regional and Global capabilities

³⁶ AP meeting documents: <https://roadsadvisorypanel.org/meeting-documents>

³⁷ <https://arcticobservingsummit.org>

³⁸ <https://arcticcircle.org>

³⁹ <https://arcticfrontiers.com>

- 2023:
 - Roadmap for Arctic observing and data systems (ROADS) process
 - Developing Shared Arctic Variables
- 2024: Roadmap for Arctic observing and data systems (ROADS) process
- 2025: Advancing the Practices of Societal Impact Assessment in Research Planning

Presentations at the European Geosciences Union (EGU):

- 2020: Roadmap for Arctic Observing and Data Systems (ROADS)
- 2021: An integrated system of observations driven by societal benefit

Group on Earth Observations (GEO) events:

- GEO Week: Session for Arctic GEOSS with the GEO Mountains Initiative (Ghana, 2022)
- GEO Ministerial: Booth organized and presentation of Arctic PASSION Pilot Services (South Africa, 2023)
- GEO Global Forum: Joint session with the GEO Mountains Initiative (Rome, 2025)

Communicating and dialogue on the ROADS process to other initiatives (not complete list):

- Authorship on the ROADS process to two deliverables under EU PolarNet: 1) *Minutes of a Workshop with Coordinators of European Polar Observing Systems*⁴⁰ (2022), and 2) *White paper with recommendations to accelerate the development of a sustained and fully integrated Polar observing system*⁴¹ (2024)
- *The Seventh International Symposium on Arctic Research (ISAR-7, 2023)*: Organizing funding for observing in the Arctic (presentation)
- Member of Science Committee for HiMAC Workshop in 2023 (<https://www.geocri.org/himac-2023>). *The 3rd International Workshop on Observations and Understanding of Changes in High Mountain and Cold Regions*. 2023.11.29-12.2 Urumqi, China. Presentation with the title *Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks' (SAON) Roadmap for Arctic Observing and Data Systems (ROADS)*
- Arctic PASSION services reported to the WMO 2024 *State of Climate Services report* (May 2024)
- The “Arena for the gap analysis of the existing Arctic Science Co-Operations” (AASCO) process: Presentations and participation in the 2025 event

⁴⁰ <https://eu-polarnet.eu/docs/d6-4-minutes-of-a-workshop-with-coordinators-of-european-polar-observing-systems/>

⁴¹ <https://eu-polarnet.eu/download/d6-7-white-paper-with-recommendations-to-accelerate-the-development-of-a-sustained-and-fully-integrated-polar-observing-system>

Annex 2. Survey

In the spring of 2025, the AP organised a survey, raising two questions: 1) *Are we doing the right thing?* and 2) *Who is this process meaningful for?* The ambition was to know this from different perspectives, including of Indigenous organisations and leaders, a research perspective and/or from a funder/planning perspective. The survey was organized in two versions. *Internals* were AP members, EP facilitators, project leads; *Externals* were the SAON Board and Committees, EP members and others interested. The summary below is based on responses as of 21st May 2025 with 10 *Internal* respondents (raw data: [.xlsx](#), [.pdf](#)) and 14 *External* respondents (raw data: [.xlsx](#), [.pdf](#)).

Identification

What is your role?

	Internal	External
Indigenous organization	1	0
Research	7	0
Funder/Planning	1	3
Research infrastructure	1	10
Resource manager / Governance	0	1
Total	10	14

What is your affiliation?

	Internal	External
Arctic nation	4	7
Non-Arctic nation	1	1
Indigenous	2	2
Organisation	3	4
Total	10	14

What is your association with the SAON or the ROADS process?

	Internal	External
Member of the SAON Board (or one of its task forces)	2	0
Member of the Arctic Data Committee (ADC) (or one of its working groups)	0	5

Member of the Committee on Observing and Networks (CON) (or one of its working groups)	0	2
Member of the ROADS Advisory Panel	4	0
Member of a ROADS Expert Panel	0	2
Expert Panel facilitator	1	
SAON Board, CON, Advisory Panel	1	
Member of CON, SAON Board, Advisory Panel, Convening an Expert Panel	1	
Member of ROADS Advisory Panel and Expert Panel	1	
Former member of ROADS Advisory Panel		1
(Blank)		1
Expert Panel coordinator		1
Leader of an Expert Panel		1
Member of the US AON Board		1
Total	10	14

Understanding the process

How much have you heard about the Arctic ROADS process?

	External (only)
1 - Poor	1
2	0
3	3
4	6
5 - Excellent	4
Total	14

Can you summarize how it was developed, by whom and who the responsible bodies are?

Summary (External only, 11 responses):

- Developed by SAON:
 - The Sustainable Arctic Observing Networks (SAON) led the development of the ROADS process, with input from its Board and the Advisory Panel
 - It was designed to support polycentric governance in defining Arctic observing requirements
- Collaborative origins:
 - Co-developed over time in partnership with organizations like:
 - The Arctic Council
 - IASC (International Arctic Science Committee)
 - NOAA, IARPC, and the US Arctic Observing Network (US AON)
 - Included feedback from events like the Arctic Observing Summit (AOS)
- Purpose and design:
 - Intended to improve collaboration, incorporate Indigenous knowledge, and align observing efforts with societal needs.
 - Developed to bring together expertise across sectors through expert panels and shared Arctic variable (SAV) frameworks
- Challenges and limitations:
 - Not equally embedded across all communities or member states
 - Some countries and sectors do not align their efforts with SAON or ROADS, instead following individual funding priorities

How would you describe the overall purpose and objectives of the ROADS process?

Summary (Internal, 9 responses):

- Optimizing observations to benefit a wide range of stakeholders.
- Defining and utilizing Shared Arctic Variables (SAVs) to enhance and sustain observation systems.
- Involving Indigenous Peoples through the ROADS process to ensure equitable, inclusive, and stepwise development.
- Establishing standardized protocols centered on shared societal benefits and Indigenous engagement.
- Creating robust implementation plans with SAON partners to address urgent Arctic issues.
- Fostering new partnerships and collaboration to increase efficiency and reduce redundancy in Arctic observations.
- Facilitating dialogue on how observations meet societal needs, building a shared community of practice.
- Developing a clear, replicable process for forming expert panels and producing usable, inclusive data networks.
- Advancing coordination, sustainability, and impact in Arctic observing through community development.

Summary (External, 11 responses):

- Overall Goal: ROADS is a collaborative framework to improve Arctic observing systems in a way that is inclusive, equitable, and impact-driven, especially for Indigenous and local communities.
- Key Functions:
 - Policy influence through framework development.
 - Align observing system design with community needs and societal benefits
 - Foster collaboration and partnerships among:
 - Indigenous Peoples
 - Researchers
 - Governments and agencies
 - Local and coastal communities
- Strategic Aims:
 - Bridge gaps between Western science and Indigenous knowledge systems
 - Enhance trust, co-production, and shared decision-making
 - Promote shared science, open data, and real-world impact
- Challenges: The concept is still fuzzy or unclear to some; terminology (e.g., "variable") may be misleading or not well understood

How would you rate these bodies in terms of having adequate authority/legitimacy to lead an Arctic road-mapping process for observing and data systems?

	External (only)
1 - Poor	1
2	3
3	3

4	6
5 - Excellent	1
Total	14

Who else should be included to enhance the legitimacy/efficacy of the ROADS process?

Summary (External only, 12 responses):

- Showcasing Outcomes: Provide concrete, accessible results (e.g., summaries of Shared Arctic Variables).
- Data Expertise: Strengthen alignment with data specialists to support expert panels.
- Inclusivity: Ensure the process reflects societal needs, particularly by involving Indigenous groups and Arctic municipalities.
- Governance & Authority: Improve coordination across fragmented authorities, and involve decision-makers from Arctic states.
- Community Input: Gather more perspectives from Arctic communities on monitoring needs.

In short, demonstrating results, improving data alignment, and including diverse stakeholders (especially Indigenous voices) would boost legitimacy and efficacy

Do you think you understand the Arctic ROADS process well enough to engage in it?

	Internal	External
1 - Poor	0	2
2	0	1
3	1	6
4	6	2
5 - Excellent	3	3
Total	10	14

How well do you think you could explain the Arctic ROADS process?

	Internal	External
1 - Poor	0	1
2	0	2

3	0	5
4	4	5
5 - Excellent	5	1
Total	9	14

What do you think is an adequate time for comments for members of the Advisory Panel back to facilitators of Expert Panels and Expert Panel members?

Summary (internal, 9 responses):

- Preferred timeframes for tasks or decisions:
 - Most responses suggest a duration of 1 month to 2 months, with several specifically mentioning 4–6 weeks, 1 month, or 60 days.
 - Some note that 2 weeks might be too short.
 - One response highlights that 1 month is desirable, but flexibility is needed due to scheduling conflicts (e.g., summer vacation).
- Ongoing commitment: Monthly 1.5-hour meetings and occasional participation in conferences, including speaking or helping host sessions.

Summary (external, 12 responses): In short, the ideal comment period varies but should be flexible, last around 30-42 days, and account for process challenges.

Do you think there has been equitable Indigenous engagement and representation within the Arctic ROADS process?

Summary (Internal, 9 responses):

- Some progress made: A few responses acknowledge that efforts have been made to involve Indigenous Peoples, and there are valuable initiatives underway.
- Engagement is insufficient or uneven:
 - Involvement is not consistent or equitable across the board.
 - True representation and co-production of knowledge are still lacking.
- Barriers identified:
 - Limited capacity of Indigenous groups to respond or participate regularly.
 - Indigenous representatives are oversubscribed and under-resourced, requiring funding and honoraria to participate.
 - The current system has not made a compelling case to Indigenous communities on why participation is worthwhile.
- Need for improvement:
 - While engagement is a clear goal, achieving equity will take time, effort, and resources.
 - There is recognition that this is a long-term process requiring better support and commitment

Summary (external, 12 responses):

The responses indicate a mix of opinions on the level of Indigenous involvement in the ROADS process:

- **Strong Engagement, But Room for Improvement:** Many agree that the ROADS process has made significant strides in involving Indigenous communities, but it could still improve, particularly in terms of equity and engagement across all Arctic communities.
- **Indigenous Leadership:** Indigenous leadership is rare in Expert Panels (EPs) and ROADS committees, and while there is an ongoing effort to improve this, it hasn't fully materialized yet. Some believe that Indigenous leadership is an essential goal but is not yet fully realized.
- **Varying Effectiveness:** There is a recognition that efforts to engage Indigenous members in the expert panels have been made, but their effectiveness in achieving meaningful participation varies.
- **Ongoing Work:** The process is a work in progress, with inclusion as a key principle, and some efforts, like hiring specific positions, are helping to increase Indigenous involvement.

In short, while Indigenous involvement in ROADS has been strong compared to other processes, there is still work to be done to fully integrate Indigenous leadership and ensure equitable participation.

Benefit and outcome of the process

What types of initiatives and activities, in your opinion, could benefit from the process?

	Internal	External
Human-related observing initiatives	0	0
Science-related observing initiatives	5	4
Indigenous-led observing initiatives	0	3
Arctic nations	0	1
Non-Arctic nations	0	0
ROADS is about shared benefits of local/indigenous, regional/national and international/science actors. So no point to raise just one	1	-
All of the above/All of them	3	3
All of the above, especially science-related (societal benefit already baked into Indigenous-led)	-	1
Why can't I select all of them?	-	1
Several of the above	-	1
Total	9	14

In the 'three-circle' infographics of Shared Arctic Variables, it is depicted how 1) Indigenous/local, 2) Regional/Arctic, and 3) Global points of view are brought together. In your view, has the process been successful in bringing these together?

	Internal	External
Yes	6	1
No	1	6
Yes;I think YES, but better to have a short explanation like this question	1	-
Yes;for some SAVs, yes	1	-
Somewhat, but not consistently	1	-
This isn't a binary yes/no. I think progress has been made but it is insufficient	1	-
I would place somewhere in the middle	1	-
Process visioning is successful, but it's hard to say without more examples of it being run start to finish	-	1
Don't know enough to to say	-	1
It's not clear to me if it's been successful and I would need a detailed overview that really gets into the data and metadata details in order for me to assess that	-	1

I think it depends on who was leading an EP and what their positionality is	-	1
Partially - and more "no" than "yes". coordination is a work in progress and there are always people who should be at the table and aren't - on many levels (geopolitical to marginalization of tribal nations)	-	1
I think it is one of the best processes I have witnessed so far. But I think there is still quite a bit of learning to be done across the board to realize the desired outcome.	-	1

A purpose of the process should be to successfully identify the most important, impactful observables that should be prioritised and funded. In your view, is this a likely outcome of the process?

	Internal	External
Yes	5	5
No	2	3
YES and NO. I think the process is going to identify the observables which can benefit both the communities AND the research/monitoring people. It doesn't always mean these variables are "most" important, though they are important ones	1	-
I hope so but I believe that clearer and closer ties have be built with funders and decision-makers	1	-
Yes;Of course it depends on the Expert Panel members, what are the observables identified and if the members were some	1	-

other people, the observables identified might be something different. Getting funding is almost always an issue		
Yes;No;yes and no, because we have several SAVs and not all are equally progressing	1	-
Still too early to say	1	-
Difficult to say, there is potential but as this is still in piloting phase it is hard to say	1	-
That's exactly the kind of outcome that I think ROADS should be able to demonstrate. However, I've yet to see any tangible outcomes of this process	-	1
Maybe - remains to be seen	-	1
Unclear at this moment. I'll be frank I have heard concerning statements from western scientists that indicate to me they are not fully engaging with these concepts, this process, or arriving at any conclusion that is not a foregone one they arrived with	-	1
Maybe in a small set of domains	-	1
Right now we're still learning how to approach the definition of "important" and go about prioritization. But hopefully some steps in this direction are an outcome of the process. More "yes" than "no"	-	1
I certainly hope so. I expect that we will realize interim success and over time realize additional improvements	-	1

If 'No', what do you see as enabling or constraining this outcome?

Summary (internal, 5 responses):

- Science-heavy focus: Some SAVs are overly focused on scientific aspects, lacking integration with societal and decision-making levels.
- Top-down approach persists: Existing structures and ongoing projects have limited bottom-up innovation and slowed progress.

- Lack of clarity and engagement:
 - The overall purpose or goals (e.g., of SAVs or ROADS) have not been clearly or consistently communicated.
 - The process does not explicitly ask stakeholders to define priority observables—only how observables are used—limiting input on what truly matters.
- Conceptual uncertainty: Some hesitation stems from confusion or ambiguity around the definitions and roles of SAVs and ROADS.

Summary (external, 6 responses):

Responses highlight skepticism about success due to challenges:

- Uncertainty: Some are unsure if success is likely without seeing results first.
- Narrow Focus: Expert panels may be too limited in scope to address broader Arctic issues.
- High Effort: Achieving shared agreement on observables will require significant time and resources.
- Visibility & Funding: Results need to be shared with key entities, but securing consistent government funding is difficult.

In short, while there's potential, concerns exist over focus, effort, and funding challenges

On phase IV ('Implementation'): If you represent a nation or a funding institution or if you know the funding situation in your nation: Is it likely that an SAV specification (as you know it) will be implemented/funded in your nation

	Internal	External
Yes	4	1
No	1	3
Yes;Yes but we have to work on mobilizing the outcomes of our efforts	1	-
Funding is almost always an issue	1	-
Yes;again, time will show, but there is a chance of success	1	-
The process is still abstract, there should be strong thrive for it	1	-
I'm not sure in this political climate (US)	-	1
Couldn't say, would have to learn more about it. Right now, no	-	1
Maybe - depends on the time scale and who is in office at the time. Under the current administration? Likely not. Also	-	1

depends on who is funding - are we talking federal, state, or private?		
Perhaps	-	1
Depends on the authoritarians	-	1
N/A	-	1
Hope	-	1
It seems unlikely that in the current environment we would be able to realize this entirely appropriate, laudable goal.	-	1

If you are a member of the Advisory Panel: Has it been clear what the expectations are?

	Internal (only)
Yes	6
No	1
No;It's becoming clearer over time	1
Yes, and No. It was not clear throughout and I struggled to understand how to help as a leading role in the process, not fully understanding myself. After ASSW, I feel like I can now look back and see where we have been and where we have come and I'm very proud of the work!	1
The role related to developing the process was great than expected	1

If 'No', what can be done in terms of introducing the process to Advisory Panel members?

- Clarifying the relationship between the overarching purpose of SAON and the purpose of ROADS would improve.

- We need better, more clear and concise communications, broader reach, clear messaging, confidence across all our members that what we are doing is important and should have a central place in developing observation networks and monitoring systems moving forward! We need more broad recognition and awareness as well

What has been your own time and effort in the process as a member of the Advisory Panel?

Summary (Internal, 9 responses):

- Level of engagement varies:
 - Some contributed consistently (e.g., 2–3 hours per week, 6 hours per month, heavy involvement in writing and facilitation)
 - Others had limited time due to competing commitments, though they still participated (e.g., responding to reviews, even if lightly).
- Types of contributions:
 - Writing guidance documents
 - Facilitating meetings and sessions
 - Providing feedback on processes
 - Offering communication and facilitation expertise
 - Engaging in co-chair or leadership roles
- Reflections:
 - Some found it challenging to define their role, especially if not directly tied to Arctic research, but felt that sharing these challenges was valuable.
 - Several expressed a desire to contribute more in the future.

Is it an issue that some of the Expert Panels are working on themes that are not within your own area of expertise?

	Internal (only)
Yes	1
No	7
This is an interesting issue, i think advisory panel should have more stakeholders. As such tje documentation should be in quite general level. As mentioned, the process is somewhat abstract and still taking its form.	1

If you are compensated for your engagement in the Advisory Panel, do you find that the compensation is sufficient?

	Internal (only)
Yes	
No	
At least, the understanding about the role as the panel member from my affiliated instituion was not enough	1
Not compensated	1
Not compensated. I would love to be able to have dedicated time to work on the AP, but doing it from the side of my desk has been ok. With more time, for instance if I were funded, I would be able to direct my time more fully to the process. I do not know that it is a huge burden on our AP members right now though. Jan, Sandy, Margaret are so productive!	1

